

Voices of Climate Adaptation

A citizen engagement journey into local climate adaptation pathways across Europe.

 Funded by the European Union

 cmcc

Voices of Climate Adaptation collects the results of **Adaptation AGORA**, a HORIZON Europe project, which supports the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

At the heart of the project are collaboration and community engagement. Citizens, civil society organizations, academics, experts, policymakers, and other stakeholders are involved in different geographies to co-design strategies to deal with local impacts of climate change. In this way the project delivers context-specific solutions, recognizing that there is no “one size fits all” in adaptation.

Who we are

The Voices of Climate Adaptation website has been created by **CMCC** within the Adaptation AGORA project.

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This **downloadable pdf (short version)** has been curated by CMCC.
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Greenish phytoplankton around Gotland, Sweden ©USGS

Themes

These themes offer a lens into the journey of adaptation that local communities and citizens are undertaking together to face the impacts of climate change. More than just a response, adaptation becomes an opportunity for collective growth, where science, policy, awareness, and active citizenship come together to shape resilient, empowered communities.

Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Science and Data

Public Awareness

Policy in the making

CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

Communities lead local adaptation through participation and co-design

Local adaptation requires communities to understand their **specific risks and vulnerabilities**, and design **tailor-made solutions** suited to their social and geographical context.

Citizen participation is key to making adaptation democratic and effective, fostering **behavioral change**, and creating feedback loops between people and institutions.

Engagement helps surface **critical issues**, influence **decision-makers**, and direct **resources** where they are most needed.

Capacity building is essential – equipping individuals and institutions with knowledge, tools, and networks for sustained action.

SCIENCE AND DATA

Robust evidence and contextual data underpin resilient adaptation

Science provides the **knowledge base** needed for effective action, enabling local actors to make **informed decisions** grounded in evidence rather than assumptions.

Continous data collection and monitoring help identify trends, vulnerabilities, and opportunities for adaptation.

Collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and citizens ensures that science remains contextual and actionable.

Digital platforms and open data **democratize access** to knowledge and enhance **transparency and accessibility** in decision-making.

CLIMATE ADAPTATION *as collective growth*

Together, these four themes show adaptation as a shared, dynamic process that shapes resilient and empowered communities.

PUBLIC AWARENESS

Awareness builds the foundation for informed action and collective responsibility

Raising awareness means helping people recognize **risks, causes, and urgency** of the climate crisis.

Awareness empowers both **communities and local authorities** to adapt and respond effectively.

Communication must be **clear, relatable, and engaging**, making use of storytelling and local examples.

Combating misinformation is a critical step toward building trust and mobilizing action.

Continuous education and peer learning equip communities with the skills needed to navigate changing climate risks, fostering shared knowledge, mutual support, and collective resilience.

POLICY IN THE MAKING

Adaptive governance ensures fairness and long-term resilience

Climate policies transform ideas and research into tangible **laws, plans, and funding**.

Good policy ensures a **just transition**, protecting vulnerable communities and reducing inequalities.

Policymaking is influenced by **many forces**: science, economy, public opinion, and politics.

Inclusive policy processes should involve citizens, stakeholders, and local actors in **co-design and implementation**.

Current challenges concern uneven participation, limited resources, and processes that do not fully include all community groups.

Radar image of Catalan coasts in Spain, from Copernicus Sentinel-1 ©ESA

Pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe: Italy, Germany, Sweden, and Spain, come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

These inspiring experiences are the result of Adaptation AGORA's work across diverse regions, engaging local communities and a broader network of over 35 followers. Together, they're tackling place-based climate challenges and co-creating practical, inclusive solutions, designed to foster collaboration, share best practices, and raise awareness.

Italy - The Eternal Resilience

Sweden - Keeping Malmö Cool

Spain - Urban and Rural Adaptation

Germany - Go where Citizens are

Four pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

Sweden

Keeping Malmö Cool

Nordic life is built for cold — bodies, homes, whole cities. But rising heat is a new, unexpected challenge changing everything. Yet a city's ability for adaptation often rises from hidden corners, places you would never expect to drive such change.

Germany

Go where Citizens are

Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But in Dresden, it became truly meaningful when we stepped into people's spaces, listened to their voices, and met them where they are, rather than expecting them to come to us.

Spain

Urban and Rural Adaptation

From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions from both dimensions bridge countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.

Italy

The Eternal Resilience

Rome has endured centuries of history, but today it faces a new trial: the relentless pressures of climate change. Can the eternal city rise once again, this time by turning crisis into opportunity?

Common participatory pathway

Diverse territories converge into one shared approach shaped through dialogue, collaboration, and local experience.

Understanding the context

Each region began by **analysing its specific climate impacts** — heatwaves, floods, droughts, and social inequalities — combining scientific data, local knowledge, and territorial assessments. This helped **identify where impacts concentrate and which communities, sectors, or ecosystems are most exposed.**

1

2

Engaging stakeholders

Workshops and consultations brought together authorities, experts, and citizens to **collect diverse perspectives**. These dialogues surfaced priorities, barriers, and lived experiences while **building trust among actors**. This engagement ensured that adaptation planning reflected **both evidence and the realities of everyday life** in each region.

3

Co-design solutions

After gaining a shared understanding of each other's perspectives, **stakeholders collaboratively developed strategies** tailored to local conditions and diverse community needs. The process allowed participants to test ideas, compare options, and shape solutions that were **not only technically sound but also feasible and meaningful** for the people involved.

4

Results

The pilots resulted in a set of **soft adaptation measures** focused on education, communication, and inclusive coordination among local actors. They strengthened **capacities**, improved **awareness**, and fostered **shared ownership** of adaptation pathways. These outcomes now support regions in advancing participatory, community-driven approaches to **long-term climate resilience**.

Italy's pathway

Rome

The Eternal Resilience

watch the video

Rome, the Eternal City. For centuries, it has stood resilient in the face of time. But can it rise once again, this time to meet the challenge of climate change? Can adaptation become a springboard for modernisation and a chance to improve the quality of life for all who live and visit here?

Unlike its beautiful stone memories, Rome is not standing still, but it has embarked on its climate adaptation journey with a dedicated local strategy.

LOCAL IMPACTS

Rising sea level

Shifting rainfall patterns

Rising temperatures

VULNERABILITIES

- **18 Km of coastline**
- **3 rivers:** Tiber and its affluents Aniene and Almone
- **5-6 °C temperature rise**
- **9% of population at risk**

RISKS & CHALLENGES

Floods

Heatwaves

Water management

Coastal erosion

Longer summers

More than 100 **STAKEHOLDERS** INVOLVED, from 4 key groups.

Municipality

Other public authorities

Civil society

Academia

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

INCEPTION WORKSHOP

FOCUS GROUPS

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

November 2023

Summer & Autumn 2024

January 2025

RESULTS

EDUCATION

PUBLIC AWARENESS

Sweden's pathway Malmö

Keeping the City Cool

watch the video

Malmö is a modern multicultural city that has reinvented itself from an industrial hub into a center of design, technology, and sustainability. Internationally recognized for integrating innovation, tradition, and green living, its landscape blends medieval heritage with contemporary architecture, symbolized by Calatrava's Turning Torso. The city-specific pathway focused on Rosengård, a low-income public housing neighborhood, revealing both vulnerabilities and strong adaptive capacities.

LOCAL IMPACTS

Rising temperatures

Rising sea level

VULNERABILITIES

- Historic **prioritization of winter-proof infrastructure**
- Unprepared **vulnerable groups of citizens**, such as elderly or outdoor workers

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

Heatwaves

Unequal impacts of urban heat

The case study brought together a diverse group of **112 STAKEHOLDERS** from civil society and academia to the private sector and non-profit organizations. **Among those, two were the key partners.**

Municipality

Public Housing Company MKB

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RESULTS

INCEPTION WORKSHOP

FOCUS GROUPS & INTERVIEWS

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

September 2023

Summer 2024

January 2025

CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

EDUCATION

Spain's pathway

Aragón region

Urban and Rural Adaptation

watch the video

The region of Aragón is an autonomous community in northeastern Spain, characterized by a remarkable variety of landscapes and renowned for its rich historical and architectural heritage. The regional capital is Zaragoza, the most populous city in Aragón, is a key hub for transportation, commerce, and logistics. Zaragoza has a semi-arid climate with Mediterranean influences. In recent years, however, the city has faced significant climate challenges, which have driven it to take proactive measures.

LOCAL IMPACTS

Rising temperatures

Extreme rainfalls

Prolonged droughts

Increase in wildfires frequencies

VULNERABILITIES

- **Semi-arid climate** rises vulnerability for **water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation, and desertification**
- Rural depopulation and **ageing communities in isolated areas**
- **Energy poverty** limiting access to essential energy services

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

Floods

Heatwaves

Urban heat island effect

Exacerbation of social inequalities

STAKEHOLDERS

who have been involved belonged to **4 key groups**.

Government of Aragón

Zaragoza City Council

University of Zaragoza

Civil Society

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

INCEPTION WORKSHOP

FOCUS GROUPS

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

September 2023

Summer 2024

February 2025

CLIMATE SHELTERS

ENERGY COMMUNITIES

INCLUSIVE AND MULTILINGUAL COMMUNICATION

RESULTS

Germany's pathway Dresden

watch the video

Go where Citizens are

Dresden, the capital of Saxony along the Elbe River, is known for its baroque architecture, cultural heritage, and extensive green spaces. Its history blends beauty and resilience, marked by fires, bombings, and major reconstruction after 1945. Today, the Altstadt (Old Town) reflects restored historic grandeur, while the Neustadt (New Town) offers a vibrant cultural and residential scene. In this context, the city has embraced a pragmatic, institution-driven approach to sustainability and climate adaptation.

LOCAL IMPACTS

Rising temperatures

Intense precipitation

Rising groundwater level

VULNERABILITIES

- **60% of territory covered in green spaces** and the city is committed to preserve it
- Location along the **Elbe river**
- **Population growth & rapid urbanization**
- **Ageing population & infrastructures**

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

Flash floods

Overloaded drainage systems

Urban heat island effect

Increased energy demand

STAKEHOLDERS

were mapped across each city region, reaching citizens in their own spaces and contexts. Those involved belonged to 4 key groups.

Municipality

Municipal Hospital

Private sector

Non-profit associations

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

INCEPTION WORKSHOP

FOCUS GROUPS

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

September 2023

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INCLUSIVE COMMUNICATION

EDUCATION

FUNDING STRATEGIES

RESULTS

www.voicesofclimateadaptation.dataclime.com